

A proposed patient-centric healthcare framework for better Semantic interoperability using Blockchain

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Abstract— Recent years have seen a paradigm shift in the data sharing and interoperability of Electronic Health Records (EHRs), especially in cloud environments. EHR systems traditionally used to exchange health information amongst healthcare stakeholders have been criticized for centralizing power, failures, and attack points with the exchange data custodians. However, this paradigm also raises many concerns about data privacy and security for e-health systems. Blockchain promises to address the many EHR challenges, primarily trust-less and secure health information exchange among stakeholders.

This study considered 15 healthcare models and frameworks based on Blockchain that discussed theoretical, technical, and architectural viewpoints that addressed interoperability, privacy, security, cost, and performance dimensions. Based on that, it presents a novel EHRs interoperability framework that combines Blockchain, cloud, and decentralized data sources among multiple healthcare ecosystems based on the strict-layered topology. The empirical results show that our framework provides an effective solution for interoperability and reliable data exchanges while preserving sensitive health information against potential threats.

Keywords— Electronic health records (EHRs), EHRs sharing, mobile cloud computing (MCC), Internet of Medical Things (IoMT), Blockchain, smart contracts, DLT, distributed ledger technology, distributed computing, interoperability, access control, privacy, security, health information management, health information exchange, digital health, eHealth.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, there has been a growing interest in employing blockchain technology to promote medical and e-health services as Blockchain has demonstrated immense potentials in various e-health sectors, such as secure sharing of Electronic Health Records (EHRs) and data access management among multiple medical entities, because of its decentralized and trustworthy nature. Therefore, the adoption of Blockchain can provide promising solutions to facilitate healthcare delivery and thus revolutionize the healthcare industry [1].

The fundamental premise of the Blockchain is the underlying information technology (IT) architecture, and it is an "unbreakable" chain of data entries that allow for secure and open transactions, as the decentralized and distributed database of a blockchain provides an auditable and distributed

ledger that allows all to see every transaction. Thus, the open-source attributes of the Blockchain make the technology a natural fit for the requirements associated with the complexities of transaction-laden systems associated with health information technology in the public and private sectors.

Zubaydi came with one comprehensive definition: "Blockchain is defined as a distinct, decentralized distributed ledger that includes all transactions records related to participating members. Blockchain transactions are created and stored in chronological order, allowing digital assets (such as digital currency and digital data) to be tracked by participants without central record-keeping" [2]. The advantages of Blockchain are apparent, but with any new technology, there are questions about efficacy and efficiency. Thus, this research attempts to answer questions about the technology, interoperability issues, and specific applications related to the healthcare space and associated security.

The following section discussing the different types of Blockchain from a technical perspective, then elaborates on the Blockchain architecture and its main components (Block, Digital Signature, Smart contract, Consensus Algorithm), moving on the role of using the Blockchain in Healthcare systems is described. Later, the healthcare industry-shifting is discussed. Finally, interoperability as a pressing issue in healthcare is discussed.

A. Types of Blockchain

From a technical perspective, Blockchain is basically categorized into three types: private, consortium, and public Blockchain. It should be noted that such categorizations are still being argued that diverse definitions might be explained in the literature.

1) Private Blockchain

A private blockchain is considered a distributed yet centralized network fully controlled by single organization. that trusted party used for private purposes enables the chosen nodes only to participate in the network. Also, it can be considered as a permissioned network that controls which nodes that can execute transactions and which nodes can perform smart contracts. Examples of blockchain platforms

that support private blockchain networks are; Hyperledger Fabric and Ripple [3].

2) Consortium Blockchain

The consortium blockchain is partly private and partially decentralized, where a preselected portion of nodes controls the consensus process. For example, for a consortium of 20 institutions, for the block validation in each operation every block must be signed by about 11 nodes, and the reading right to the participants for the Blockchain may be public or restricted. Conversely, a consortium between, financial and governmental institutions and insurance companies has established a partially centralized trust, in addition to being opened for public use. Examples of this blockchain type; Hyperledger, R3, Ethereum, and Solidity [4].

3) Public Blockchain

Blockchain is accessible and visible to the public where all the data in the public and permissionless that is often called just public. where anyone can act as a simple node and join the Blockchain without any approval. Though, in Blockchain some parts could be encrypted for preserving the anonymity of participants. These blockchains types are usually given an economic incentive, like what is happening in cryptocurrency networks. Examples of this type of Blockchain are; Litecoin or Bitcoin [5].

B. The Architecture of Blockchain

The of the architecture elements may differ depending on the used Blockchain type. For example, a Blockchain holds a complete list of transaction records in a sequence of blocks similar to a conventional public ledger. An example of a blockchain is illustrated in fig 1, where each block has only one parent block with a block header containing the previous block hash [6]; the Blockchain's first block is called the genesis block, which does not has a parent block. Later, the internals of Blockchain will be explained in detail.

Figure 1 Simple Blockchain example consists of a continuous sequence of blocks [6]

1) Block

The Blockchain highly assists a distributed ledger in transaction recording, attributing them to a particular node in a network, and calling them in time. Then in the network, data is recorded permanently through files entitled blocks that record all or some of the latest transactions that have yet to be recorded in earlier blocks. Thus, the previous transactions' ledger is called Blockchain, as it represents to a chain of blocks.

Each block composed of two main parts: block body and block header. On the one hand, the block body contains

transaction counter and transactions; the size of the block depends on both; the maximum number of transactions that a block can contain and the size of each transaction. In addition, an asymmetric cryptography mechanism is used to validate the authentication of transactions. On the other hand, the block header comprises multiple elements; Merkle tree root hash, block version, timestamp, and the previous block hash.

2) Digital Signature

A transaction creation on the *Blockchain* needs a digital signature for transaction authentication. A standard digital signature encompasses two phases: signing phase and verification phase. Each user holds a pair of *keys*, a public key, and a private key. For confidentiality, the private key should be kept that is used for signing transactions. Thus because, the digitally signed transactions are broadcasted throughout the whole network [7], in an untrustworthy environment raised the importance of applying the asymmetric cryptography exposed by the digital signature.

3) Node

The dealings between users on Blockchain mainly use a decentralized network wherein each user act for a node at which a blockchain client is installed. When two users are performing a transaction with each other or when one node receives data from another, it verifies the data authenticity, and then the validated data is broadcasted to every other connected node. Within such a mechanism, the data spread across the whole network. The benefit of using this mechanism is minimizing the human factor centralization, and trust moves from central organization human agents to an open-source code [4].

4) Smart contract

A smart contract (smart contract) is a specific computer code built into the Blockchain network and executed by computers or nodes. When the terms between the parties in the smart contract are written in the form of code in the Blockchain. With the anonymous parties involved, but the contract itself has public properties. For example, when a starting event, such as the occurrence of a specific date or the achievement of a given price, the contract launches itself based on the provisions recorded in its code, the network nodes update the register, the contract is automatically closed, and information about the actions performed is recorded in the Blockchain [8].

5) Consensus Algorithm

In a network, Blockchain requires all users' acceptance and verification as each node has diverse views of the whole network state. Consequently, reaching consensus in distributed mechanisms is a considerable challenge for Blockchain development, where multiple consensus algorithms can be applied. So, in order to remain functional for the blockchain network, its peers need to accept a particular state of the distributed ledger and also agree upon the technique used for packing data into blocks. Such an agreement is termed a distributed consensus protocol; as the generated transactions' chronological order is validated in

addition to ensuring that a quorum peers of blockchain network (consensus) agree on the precise state of the shared ledger, and the order of adding new blocks to the ledger [9].

C. Blockchains in Healthcare and Electronic Health Records (EHR)

Over the earlier decade, the need for sheer increment in digitizing medical health records was caused by medical practitioners, hospitals, and healthcare devices, as data digitization enables easy access, sharing and also considered as the base for quick and better decision making. Thus currently the Electronic Health Records (EHRs) became the most common healthcare applications of blockchain technologies [10] as illustrated in fig 2 below.

Figure 2 A depiction of Blockchain in Healthcare and Electronic Health Record [10]

Though, EHRs were never formed to deal with lifetime records among various institutions. Because of leaving patients' data between several institutions as life circumstances separate them from one provider's data into another; like this, they miss easy access to previous data. So, an innovative way to handle EHRs was a critical necessity for encouraging patients to participate in their current and historical healthcare data; thus, blockchain technology have been brought up by many researchers for maintaining the EHRs [11].

D. Healthcare industry-shifting

The healthcare industry is shifting from volume-based care (fee-for-service) to value-based care. Where in volume-based care providers were incentivized to provide more treatments as payment is relative to the quantity of care provided, while in value-based care patient-centered care is promoted with higher quality (hence "value") as patients become involved in clinical decision making.

In the patient-centered care model, patients are able to incorporate both; Patient Recorded Outcome Measures (PROM) and Patient Reported Experience Measures (PREM) [12], for instance health status or symptoms that gathered from their mobile and wearable devices and stored into their medical history. Especially after the COVID-19 situation over the lob patients required access to their entire medical history with a widespread view, which shrinks information fragmentation and imprecision caused by delays in communication or coordination mistakes and improves care quality and continuity, ideally, all health systems (regardless of the type of care settings) would afford spontaneous

notifications for patients providing (near) real-time access to their clinical data, e.g., once lab results become available or when records are entered into the system. In addition, for patient-centric care it is essential for patients to govern to whom and when their health data is shared and to select what pieces of information, they would be agreeable to share. However, healthcare systems today do not offer the means for patients to change or disable a provider's access to their data.

E. Interoperability as a Pressing Issue in Healthcare

Healthcare interoperability describes the capability for various information technology systems and software applications to interconnect, interchange data, and use them. In addition, allowing information systems to work together within and across organizational boundaries is paramount to improve effective care delivery for individuals and communities. For example, interoperability enables providers to securely and scalable share patient medical records with one another (given patient permissions to do so), regardless of provider location and trust relationships between them. Sharing data securely and scalable is crucial offering effective collaborative care for patients' decisions [13]. Sharing data supports increased diagnostic accurateness and precluding shortages and inaccuracies in the treatment plan and medication. Likewise, aggregated intelligence and insights help clinicians recognize patient's requirements and, in turn, more effective treatments can be applied [14].

Despite the significance of sharing medical data, today's healthcare systems repeatedly involve patients to get their medical records and share them with other providers, either through soft electronic copies or physical paper copies. Nevertheless, obtaining and sharing medical records in this way is ineffective for the reasons discussed below [15]:

- Slow - as medical data copies must be arranged, transmitted, and hand-picked by patients.
- Insecure - as medical data copies throughout their physical transmission by patients from one location to another may be stolen or lost.
- Incomplete - as patient health data history is stored in siloed and disparate systems that make them fragmented. Also, the absence of a single repository that stores all the patient's medical records and the patient's responsibility for keeping track of when and where health services were received to demand copies of their medical data history.
- Lack of context - as today's healthcare systems are provider-centric rather than patient-centric, patients are prevented from controlling their health records and knowing who, when, and how their data have been accessed and modified.

1) Interoperability Levels

Apart from the lack of interoperability between health IT applications and systems and the lack of trust that occurs today, providers result in the inefficient data-sharing process in healthcare. Thus, Healthcare interoperability comprises three levels of data exchange: foundational, structural, and semantic, ordered lowest to highest fidelity.

Table 1 Summary of the Three Levels of Interoperability [15]

Interoperability Level	Summary
Foundational Interoperability	Data exchange is enabled; does not require data interpretation
Structural Interoperability	Defines formats for the exchanged data
Semantic Interoperability	Requires interpretation of the exchanged data

As been illustrated in table 1, Foundational interoperability enables data exchanges between healthcare systems. It does not require providers receiving the data to be able to interpret the data. Structural interoperability also defines formats for exchanged clinical data and ensures that received data are preserved and interpretable using predefined formats at the data field level. Semantic interoperability demands the interpretability of exchanged data by syntax (structure) and semantics (meaning).

These three levels help ensure that disparate health systems and applications deliver information with requisite data quality and safety. Foundational and structural interoperability are prerequisites for semantic interoperability, which is hardest to achieve but most desired to advance the quality of care. This framework focuses on the semantic interoperability, which requires clinical domain knowledge and medical policies that enforce the adoption of ontologies.

The remaining of this paper are organized such that the research detailed literature review, as we are describing the main 15 published frameworks and model in the healthcare industry that was designed based on the Blockchain networks. We used the proposed framework section to expand on and provide a detailed description of our solution. The conclusion section was used to summarize the study while laying the foundation for future work.

II. RELATED WORK

In a traditional clinical trial data management system, a unique identification number is generated and appended to the corresponding entry on the database when a subject is enrolled. A schedule of activities for each visit is generated by the personal information (PI) and sensitive personal information (SPI). The application has a tracking and notification system which can advise clinic staff on subject follow-up windows and required laboratory activities. Tracking a subject begins at screening and continues throughout the trial. During each visit, data is collected in the form of questionnaires, samples, and lab results.

The participating clinic sites use the application to update data from paper-based forms and questionnaires. The data entry system is designed to mirror the forms for the accuracy of data entry. This is linked to a database that the coordinating center manages at a central location. Such a framework is prone to risk a single point of failure (SPOF) and data loss. Following a subject visit, the clinic coordinator reviews the required forms and laboratory reports for accuracy and completeness. If the data entered by the clinic staff is overridden, it is flagged for review by the coordinator. The

database can also be accessed by the data and safety monitoring board (DSMB), which reviews the trial and cases of serious adverse events (SAE) to provide recommendations for continuing the trial and clinical performance [16].

Due to the growing interest in using distributed ledger technologies for health IT systems. This section summarizes this related work and compares it with our framework.

Zhang et al. [17] proposed a decentralized application (DApp) for Smart Health (DASH) design for blockchain-based applications that can improve healthcare interoperability using familiar software patterns like Abstract Factory, Flyweight, Proxy, and Publisher-Subscriber. It provides essential access services to two types of users' patients and providers. Zhang did not address three main dimensions of decentralized applications in healthcare in this proposed framework: security, dependability, and performance.

Sethi [18] proposed a healthcare framework that combines streams of technology; Data Analytics, Artificial Intelligence, and Blockchain which creates WEB 3.0 Ecosystem, Blockchain (Distributed Ledger) that play a significant role in transforming Healthcare Ecosystem and maintaining the individuals' health records efficiently. Thus, all the institutions and organizations in the healthcare domain will be interconnected with governmental permission to join the private healthcare blockchain network. Although the framework idea is brilliant, no detailed design or reference architecture filed to realize those goals developed yet.

Esposito et al. [19] presented a solution for healthcare that is based on the cloud for data security and privacy by leveraging the advantages of Blockchain that is secure by design and provides the capability to achieve decentralized consensus, consistency, and resilience to intentional or unintentional attacks, control the patient's data by their own, and agreements can be reached without the involvement of a trusted mediator. Therefore, performance bottleneck and a single point of failure are avoided. The existing limitations associated with a blockchain-based approach that needs to be carefully studied and highlighted through the proposed framework adds to the potential implications, legal and financial, thus for those healthcare providers who need to undertake a cost-benefit analysis to understand the return on investment, so more detailed studies and implementation need to confirm the success of the model.

Chen et al. [20] proposed a medical service model with secure storage and sharing for medical records based on Blockchain, which is noticed as a supply chain for data storage wherein every operation is accountable, confirmed, immutable, and cost controllable. This framework solves the medical data scattering issue in different medical institutions known as the information island phenomenon. It becomes challenging for patients to obtain all their medical records from those different medical institutions. So, such intrinsic characteristics make it a prospective solution for healthcare data systems concerned with sharing patient's medical records and keeping them private.

Mamoshina et al. [21] proposed an approach/roadmap to decentralize and accelerate biomedical research and healthcare

based on converging Blockchain and next-generation artificial intelligence technologies.

Bellod Cisneros [22] presents public health surveillance using decentralized technologies that briefly introduce the data sharing importance in the public health surveillance context and proposes a decentralized solution that can provide interoperability between several partners concerned with privacy and aim to share data. Several implications arise from this approach that needs to be addressed; institutional partners are needed to join the system, technical challenges concerning the blockchain network interfaces need to be defined, the sensitive data privacy and security role, and the decentralization impact in the organizational infrastructure for eliminating inefficiencies of sharing data.

Theodouli et al. [23] proposed a system design that allows sharing healthcare data and provide an auditable, private and secure way for management permission through leveraging from the Blockchain technology's unique properties. Also, the system's security is improved by allowing the entities requesting data to check the accessed data's integrity with the support of the Blockchain infrastructure. Additionally, the proposed system enhances multiple frames; patient data integrity, patient pseudonymity, accountability, auditing, and workflow automation.

Dwivedi et al. [24] introduced a decentralized privacy-preserving healthcare blockchain for IoT. This new hybrid approach combines the advantages of multiple cryptographic primitives such as private key, public key, Blockchain, and many others for sake of developing a patient-centric access control that enhance electronic medical records. However, the IoT resource constraints were the key challenges on the way to answer such problems.

Leeming et al. [25] present a Personalizing Healthcare Using Blockchain Technology "Ledger of Me" enabling patients to use the data to support their care and provide a reliable consent mechanism for sharing data between different organizations and applications. "Ledger of Me" is based on the principle of combining; event-driven smart contracts, medical record data, and patient control that is important for the adoption of the blockchain-based solution for the Personal Health Record (PHR) and can serve as the basis for a range of future blockchain-based medical application architectures.

Chakraborty et al. [26] suggested a framework that provides secure healthcare system design by using Blockchain technology for anomaly detection through amalgamating the Internet of Things (IoT), Machine Learning, and Blockchain. The methodology demonstrated is a system that intercepts and fetches the data generated by the wearable devices worn by the patient using the Internet of Things module. Then the Blockchain system is utilized by storing and maintaining the patients' data in the form of multiple transactions and support access control for the different stakeholders. The Machine Learning model is used for anomaly detection and to forecast specific scenarios that may arise by the data analysis in due course of time based on the parameters that the Doctors pass on for essential identification of the conditions faced by the patients.

Shen et al. [27] proposed MedChain, a patient-driven healthcare data-sharing framework that shows its advanced efficiency in sharing data without a security compromise via a session-based data sharing scheme, a dual-network architecture, and a digest chain structure. Thus, integrating the new inter-organizational data sharing solution with the legacy systems rather than discarding. this idea was extended by MedChain through developing a scalable decentralized framework without trusting a third party and maximizing all parties' interests by including data streams from several tracking devices, that later on will support doctors and medical researchers.

Abdellatif et al. [28] presented a novel innovative and secure Healthcare system (ssHealth), leveraging advances in edge computing and blockchain technologies, permitting epidemics discovery, remote monitoring, and fast emergency response. The proposed system allows secure medical data exchange using a blockchain-based architecture. It enables a flexible configuration that optimizes medical data sharing between different health entities and fulfills the diverse levels of Quality of Service (QoS) that ssHealth may require. Additionally, they defined a novel mechanism that can be implemented within the blockchain network to ensure fast response, scalability, and secure transmission of medical data. Also, it is shown that mapping the characteristics of the collected data onto appropriate configurations of the Blockchain can significantly enhance the performance of the overall ssHealth system while satisfying diverse applications' requirements. One important feature is the multi-channel blockchain network, where each channel corresponds to a separate chain of transactions and can be used for enabling data access and private communications among the channel users.

Veeramakali et al. [29] proposed an effective optimal deep-learning-based secure blockchain(ODLSB) model for a secure blockchain-enabled intelligent IoT and healthcare diagnosis model. Initially, data are collected from the users through IoT devices. Then secret image sharing based on an orthogonal particle swarm optimization (OPSO) algorithm takes place. After this, hash value encryption is carried out using the HVE-NIS algorithm. At last, the OPSO-DNN-based disease diagnosis is executed to identify the disease. They performed detailed experiments using a benchmark dataset to validate the outcomes of the proposed method. Thus, the proposed model has performed a secured transmission of medical images and attained the highest PSNR value out of all the models considered.

Banotra et al. [30] proposed a model for the healthcare industry based on using both Blockchain and IoT technology. IoT devices measure and collect real-time data, which is then stored in the Blockchain. Also, the various billing and insurance claim concerns could easily be addressed barring all fraudulent activities. The proposed architecture addresses these concerns as blockchain technology is used for decentralization and distribution. The recorded transactions are permanently immutable, and the correspondence between the systems is encrypted. As of now, the energy consumption

by IoT devices is more. Also, the latency of adding a block in a blockchain can be shortened by utilizing quicker, increasingly effective algorithms for encryption and faster processors

Table 2 Comparison of the existing Blockchain based healthcare frameworks

#	Author	Focus Area	Framework	Type	Storage	Pros	Cons
1	Yang & Yang 2017 [31]	Sharing Health Information Security and privacy	Ethereum	Public	On-Chain	Signcryption, Attribute-Based Authentication	Shallow proposal, No implementation provided
2	Zhang et al. 2017 [17]	Sharing Health Information	Ethereum	Public	Off-Chain	Design details provide. Interoperability, Software patterns	Not tackle essential aspects like security, dependability, and performance
3	Sethi 2018 [18]	Remote care with IoT	Generic	Private	Off-Chain	Analytics and AI, which creates WEB 3.0 Ecosystem	High-level proposal
4	Esposito et al. 2018 [19]	Sharing Health Information	Generic	-	Off-Chain	Keeps the existing platform as is	Do not solve the information island phenomenon
5	Chen et al. 2018 [20]	security and privacy	Hyperledger	Consortium	-	Generic approach	High-level proposal
6	Mamoshi na et al. 2018 [21]	Remote care with IoT	Exonum	-	Off-Chain	Public health surveillance solve interoperability problem	Institutional partners mandated join the system, technical challenges concerning the blockchain network interfaces need to be defined
7	Bellod Cisneros 2018 [22]	Remote care with IoT	-	Consortium	Off-Chain	Multiple frames, Workflow automation	Very high-level proposal
8	Theodou li et al. 2018 [23]	Sharing Health Information	Ethereum	Private	On-Chain	Advanced security technique	No framework
9	Dwivedi et al. 2019 [24]	Remote care with IoT	-	-	Off-Chain	Event-driven smart contracts	Reference architecture only
10	Leeming et al. 2019 [25]	Sharing Health security and privacy	-	Private	On-Chain	Layered architecture	Using old technology
11	Chakraborty et al. 2019 [26]	Sharing Health Information Remote care with IoT	-	Consortium	-	Data sharing	Data movement issue
12	Shen et al. 2019 [27]	Sharing Health Information	-	-	Off-Chain	Proof of Familiarity (PoF) consensus gathering algorithm	Off-chain data.
13	Abdellatif et al. 2020 [28]	Sharing Health Information security and privacy	-	-	On-Chain	Edge computing, flexible configuration	No implementation details
14	Veeramkali et al. 2021 [29]	Remote care with IoT	Ethereum	-	-	Effective ODLSB model	No details related to Blockchain

15	Banotra et al. 2021 [30]	Remote care with IoT	-	-	-	Layered architecture	Energy consumption by IoT devices is more
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Table 2 provides a summary of healthcare data management mechanisms in blockchain technology since 2017 till now. Many research-work was developed to design blockchain technology to secure, share, and store EHR data both within and across institutions. Yang & Yang [31], Zhang et al. [17], Theodouli et al. [23], and Veeramakali et al. 2021 [29] proposed Ethereum based consortium Blockchain, on the other hand Chen et al. [20] used Hyperledger based consortium Blockchain, the other frameworks didn't specify the implementation framework and keeps it as a generic viewpoint. Banotra et al. [30] start to discuss the use of layered architecture in the framework which facilitate the distribution of the component functionalities, although it is still not matured layering.

III. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

Blockchain architecture supports proper medical research by maintaining the health status of the patient's identification and providing authenticated and trusted data. This framework proposed the use of the blockchain network to intercept and fetch the data that have been generated from different healthcare systems through different medical systems, health information systems, wearable devices worn by the patient. Thus, it is preferably utilized for the patient's data to be stored and maintained in the form of multiple transactions for supporting access control to\by different stakeholders.

In this framework, the layered architecture pattern is used, which provides a logical structuring mechanism for the elements that make up the software solution with a limited component scope where the components within a specific layer are well-defined. For example, components in the presentation layer deal only with presentation logic, whereas components residing in the business layer deal only with business logic. Thus, dealing only with a logic that pertains to that layer makes it easy to build influential roles and responsibility models into the architecture and the easiness to develop, test, govern, and maintain applications using this architecture pattern because of its component interfaces.

A. System Entities

In this part all the concerned entities, along with their incentives to use the system, the trust level between them, and the expected Blockchain model are analyzed. Starting from the patients who are the main driver for building and sharing healthcare data, Healthcare providers who provide health services to the patients, Healthcare insurance companies offering insurance coverage between the patients and the healthcare providers, Validators who provide the auditing facilities as well as the overall governance process, Ending with the medical research center that aims to understand the current situation of the patient case and support the researchers for further investigations. As shown below in fig 3

illustrates an overview of the proposed blockchain framework system entities.

Figure 3: Blockchain framework healthcare system entities

1) Patient (Citizen)

The patient owns his health data and has the authority to permit, reject, and cancel other parties from accessing data, such as healthcare providers and insurance companies. Also, he can check past transactions and filter historical data notifying when, and what information have been accessed and by whom.

Patients desire to share their healthcare data vary according to their intentions from using Blockchain either for medical research enhancing in general, the positive influence on their healthcare treatment, or for its consequences in the long run. Moreover, patients do not desire to compromise their security and privacy when sharing them with other parties. Thus, according to the design of the proposed system, there is no substantial overhead for those patients desire to share their data with the Blockchain network. So, dedicated Web / Cloud Platforms are used for exporting the patient data in the appropriate format.

2) Healthcare Provider

Once a particular citizen (patient) appoints healthcare providers such as doctors to perform a medical examination, provide recommendations, or offer medical treatment. In the meantime, the medical treatment data can be uploaded to the Blockchain network for sharing data with healthcare providers under the user's permission. Furthermore, the existing healthcare provider can request access from the user to their prior medical treatment and health data. So, every data request and its equivalent accessed data is logged on the Blockchain.

3) Health Insurance Company

A patient may demand a health insurance quotation from health insurance companies or agencies to pick a suitable health insurance plan. Then, the Insurance companies ask

users to access their data, including their health data from medical treatment history and wearable devices, to provide superior insurance plans. Thus, a patient with prior medical treatment(s) may require paying a higher rate and cannot deny the history to avoid insurance fraud. Also, the patient is allowed not to share their exercise information owing to privacy issues, but they mostly wish to converse their regular exercise because it can reduce their insurance payment rate. Yet, users cannot fleece or change their medical treatment data history as those data are perpetually recorded on the blockchain network, ensuring both trustworthiness and integrity. Furthermore, on the framework the insurance claims can also be recorded.

4) Medical research centers

Medical research centers seeking access to the Healthcare data stored on Clinical Platforms for research purposes. like, using a shared data pool to define demographic associates or improve medicine practices accuracy. However, they are not trusted by default, so an off-chain Identity verification is needed before being approved as nodes of the Blockchain network.

5) Validators

Validators are a subdivision of the Healthcare network/ministry that verify and validate the healthcare

transactions and ensure that everything is well established and in place.

B. System Design

In this section, architectural layers, components, and interactions among the components of our proposed system are presented. The proposed framework is composed of 5 main layers as shown in figure 4; the External (Public) Network Layer, wherein anyone, namely the public, has access and can connect to other networks; this can be considered as the external door to the user to join/access the network. The Core Network Layer is composed of the healthcare data repository, which may be on-premises, cloud, hybrid-cloud, multi-cloud environment, this layer is considered the engine of the network as the actual data resides and business logic executes. The Enterprise (Internal) Network Layer is the internal network for the healthcare systems that the framework should integrate with. The Network Governance Layer is responsible for all security aspects and the governance across all other framework layers where most of the non-function requirements (NFRs) takes place. A Connectivity and Transformation Layer is needed to integrate those layers to handle both the connectivity/network issues and transformation processes between source and target systems.

Figure 4 The Proposed framework Architecture

A large system may have tens of thousands of such components spread across millions of lines of code; therefore, complex relationships exist between these system components. The two layers interact dynamically at an interface where many different commands are being executed and processed simultaneously, defining how they exchange instructions or results.

1) Layer 1: External (Public) Network Layer

The first and topmost layer is composed of user and application interface components that interact with the other

tiers preceding it for providing content presentation services to the end-user through User Interface (UI) or Application Programming Interface (API) that can be accessed through any client device type like desktop, laptop, tablet, mobile, thin client or through an integration point with existing systems. Thus, the relevant web pages should be fetched by the web browser or other presentation component running on the client device to display the content to the user. In addition, they can export Patient data in a format appropriate for exchange over Restful Web Services.

2) Layer 2: Core Network Layer

This is the consortium Blockchain network. The smart contracts that administer the data sharing and permission management are deployed in this Blockchain network. Thus, the main components of this layer are the Blockchain Hyperledger network, rule-based engine, reporting engine, security gateway, event management, and system management. The framework's main components layer is highly customized, which can be on-premises, a specific cloud vendor, a mix between multiple cloud providers in multi-cloud environments, or a mix between on-premises and cloud environment hybrid-cloud environment. Below are the main key differentiators for each environment, considering that this can be customized according to the implementation strategy.

a) On-Premises

An On-Premises environment enables an organization to place its applications on a local data center, and then data security will always be paramount. Thus, the decision to house applications on-premises is suitable for those businesses in highly regulated industries; knowing your healthcare information is located within your in-house servers and IT infrastructure might also provide more peace of mind.

b) On-Cloud

A cloud-based server utilizes virtual technology to host an organization's applications offsite. There are no capital expenses, data can be backed up regularly, and organizations only must pay for the resources used. So, for those organizations that plan for an aggressive expansion on a global basis, the cloud solution will have a greater appeal because of its ability to connect with customers, partners, and other businesses anywhere with minimal effort.

c) Multi-Cloud

Not all clouds are created equal; hence, some healthcare organizations choose to tap several cloud models or providers, such as IBM, Google, or Microsoft Azure Cloud, at the same time. Multi-cloud solutions can offer providers more flexibility and scalability in their infrastructure.

d) Hybrid-Cloud

Many healthcare organizations balk at the idea of placing all data into a public cloud. Nevertheless, despite offering control and visibility over data, the private cloud does not afford the scalability and flexibility that the public cloud can deliver. Hence, many healthcare organizations have begun turning to a hybrid cloud model, including a mixture of public and private cloud services. The components of a hybrid cloud typically work together where data and processes tend to intermingle and intersect in a hybrid environment. Unlike the hybrid cloud model, a multi-cloud model, different clouds are used for different tasks, so the usage typically remains in its "own" cloud's silo.

3) Layer 3: Network communication Layer

This layer plays a strategic role in the applicability and deplorability of the framework. It provides the dynamic part of the network that provides the ability to integrate with the existing healthcare system with no or minimal modification of the source system. Moreover, it provides the transformation functions that convert the non- or semi-standard health data

records to the standard form, making them readable to be stored in the Blockchain unified healthcare record.

a) Connectivity component

The connectivity component ensures that all the components technically communicate in the right way with a transport protocol that fits the required interfaces for the supplier component interfaces.

b) Transformation component

Alongside the component connectivity, the transformation component takes place, which is responsible for transformations among the framework, the protocol, message standard, or even format.

4) Layer 4: Network Governance Layer

In any large-scale solution, governance takes a vital role alongside security and monitoring, which are the procedures and policies that govern the operation of the blockchain network. After the network participants agree upon these policies, they are stored and executed from this layer that has access to most network layers. Also, the security policy and standards are in place to secure the blockchain platform and its ecosystems. Moreover, monitoring, analytics, and automation tools respond to changes in the platform and environment, requiring system capacity and error analytics.

5) Layer 5: Enterprise (Internal) Network Layer

Enterprise network traditionally centered on Local Area Network (LAN) standards with hardware switches, router devices, ethernet cabling, WIFI connections, and integrated firewall all commonly used to create LANs where multiple computers are connected to share resources like internet connections, printers, software, and files.

In a nutshell, this layer represents the healthcare organization's internal network which contains the software and databases for the health information systems. It is considered out of our scope, but understanding it facilitates communication between the proposed framework and the in-house software and data stores.

CONCLUSION

This paper proposes and analyzes a Multi-tier Blockchain architecture to secure healthcare data and its interoperability. The first layer in our architecture is the External (Public) Network Layer, which connects users to the network. The second layer (Core Network) saves the healthcare information. The third layer (Enterprise (Internal) Network) realizes the multiple healthcare providers' networks and systems. The fourth layer (Network Governance) is the governance component of the framework. Finally, the fifth layer (Connectivity and Transformation) caring about connectivity-related issues and transformation processes for the exchanged healthcare information. By adopting the structure of the proposed framework, the recording of any EHR changes on the health information keeps patients' data safe from being tampered with and enables easily accessible, integrate, and transparent audit information for the patients, hence the interoperability goals achieved by adoption this proposed framework.

V. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

As a proposed framework, there is ample room for future work. A natural first step would be a simulation environment to help gauge the outcomes of the framework. Furthermore, in-depth comparative analysis with some existing proof-of-concepts (POCs), implementations, and frameworks would show the effectiveness of our framework. Moreover, a practical implementation of the proposed framework with a POC or Minimal Viable Product (MVP) and assess the actual outcomes and limitations of the proposed healthcare framework. The work in healthcare blockchain is still in its infancy, with little work presented thus far. A simulation environment can assist as a natural next step in demonstrating specific interoperability, security, performance limitations, computation complexity, and overhead communication goals in the healthcare environment.

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